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1 Introduction

The aim of the study is to collect data for SWOT analysis of the results of LUXWEX Projects¹ in terms of their applications on Earth. The report collected key data for completing the SWOT (such as determining the TRL level of LUXWEX Technology, the risk of implementing innovative new technologies, data on the market, the problem with water and competitive solutions from other university projects) and presenting recommendations. At the end of the report, recommendations (road map) regarding possible further steps regarding LUXWEX technology are included in order to increase the chances for its implementation.

¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101081937>

2 Results of LUXEX project

The LUXEX project (Validation of Lunar Water Extraction and Purification Technologies for In-Situ Propellant and Consumables Production) is financed under the Horizon Europe Framework Program and conducted by the German Aerospace Center in Bremen in cooperation with the Technical University of Braunschweig, Liquefier Systems Group GmbH, Scanway Sp. z o. o., Thales Alenia Space Italia and the Wroclaw University of Science and Technology.

The result of the LUXEX Project is a complete system (hereinafter: Technology) for obtaining water in orbital conditions. The Technology consists of several subsystems (modules) and each of these modules is designed in such a way as to be an integral part of the entire system. The idea of the solution is that they can be implemented separately when considering terrestrial application. The system consists of:

- obtaining water from Lunar regolith (rock) module
- water purification module
- water quality monitoring module
- storage module

Process chain, and the project scope of LUXEX is shown in **Figure 1**. But, module for obtaining water from regolith (rock) in the present analysis is not considered.

Figure 1. Simplified schematic of an ISRU water process chain, and the project scope of LUXEX.²

As stated in the Grant Agreement: “The purification subsystem itself consists of multiple treatment steps (most likely four). First the raw water is pushed through filters of different mesh size (e.g. one with 10 µm and one with 2 µm) in order to remove dust particles and other solids. Following filtration, a reverse osmosis module and an ion exchange resin module are incorporated to remove ions from the raw water. The water exits the purification subsystem as purified water, which is stored in a second tank. At this stage the system border of LUXEX ends but the purified water could then be utilized for propellant production via electrolysis or as life supporting consumable.” (...) “Either a mass spectrometer or Laser Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy (LIBS) device analyses the composition of the vapour coming from the water extraction subsystem. The liquid water (raw and purified) is monitored with the in-line sensors (e.g. temperature, pH, conductivity, ion-selective) but also by taking water samples and analysing them in the water quality measurement devices of the laboratory grade (e.g. turbidity).”

The system as a whole is designed for relatively low water extraction efficiency and consequently low flow in the system at the level of several to several dozen cm³/h. It results from the specificity of the process of obtaining water from the regolith (thawing, evaporation, condensation).

The Technology also includes description of the technical conditions of each (mentioned above) subsystem intended to operate within the entire system.

² Grant Agreement-101081937-LUXEX and conversations with the scientific team from WUST

According to LUXEX Project data³, the TRL of the Technology is expected to reach level 4 (TRL=4). At the date of this report, no examination of the state of the art or patent purity has been performed. The Technology is currently in the form of a know-how. The possible absence of obstacles (conflicts with other patents, freedom to operate) in the implementation of the Technology hasn't been determined yet. Moreover, there has not yet been assigned any entity (among the consortium members) to manage the commercialization of the Technology.

³ <http://www.luwex.space/>

3 Technology Readiness Level (TRL)

Technology readiness level (TRL) is a method for estimating the maturity of technologies during the acquisition phase of a program. TRLs enable consistent and uniform discussions of technical maturity across different types of technology⁴. The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) was promoted by NASA and was next adopted by government agencies and industries across the USA and Europe.⁵

Technology readiness level according to the HORIZON 2020 – WORK PROGRAMME 2014-2015⁶:

- TRL 1 – basic principles observed
- TRL 2 – technology concept formulated
- TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept
- **TRL 4 – technology validated in lab**
- TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
- TRL 6 – technology demonstrated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
- TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment
- TRL 8 – system complete and qualified
- TRL 9 – actual system proven in operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies; or in space)

It should be noted that the TRL scale should be specified for specific fields of science - e.g. biotechnology, medicines, informatics or software. The above scale is a base, good for technical/engineering projects.

As mentioned earlier the Technology as a whole is designed for relatively low water extraction efficiency, and consequently, low flow in the system at the level of several to several dozen cm³/h. This is justified because of the process of obtaining water from the regolith (thawing, evaporation, condensation) - the main goal of the Luxex Project. The Technology has been so far tested by the Project's Partners in a laboratory scale. To summarize - based on the data above and on the WUST science team and Grant Agreement of LUXEX Project, the Technology is on TRL=4.

⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Technology_readiness_level

⁵ System Readiness Level Estimation of Oil and Gas Production Systems, Sirous F. Yasseri, Hamid Bahai; Brunel University London; Sirous.Yasseri@Brunel.ac.uk; Brunel University London; Hamid Bahai@Brunel.ac.uk, INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF COASTAL & OFF-SHORE ENGINEERING IJCOE Vol.2/No. 2/Summer 2018 (31-44)

⁶ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2014_2015/annexes/h2020-wp1415-annex-g-trl_en.pdf

4 WACC – technology implementation risk

The Technology implementation risk is related to the technology readiness level (TRL) and the market data. This risk is included in WACC.

WACC (*weighted average cost of capital*) is a rate that reflects risk related to the investment. It is calculated as a weighted average of the expected cost of debt capital and equity capital, considering the estimated financing structure of the project/investment.

Generally, WACC comes from the stock market, where there is an easy access to information on the market valuation of individual companies (market data). The WACC methodology assumes that each investment (business project) can be financed by a spectrum of sources differing in the required rate of return. The methodology for determining WACC is shown in **Figure 2** below.

Figure 2. The WACC methodology.⁷

Market **WACC** is determined according to the formula:

$$WACC = f_e * R_e + f_d R_d (1 - T_c) \quad (1)$$

Where:

- f_e - is the percentage (%) share of the cost of equity in the investment
- f_d - is the percentage (%) share of the cost of external capital in the investment
- T_c - income tax for the company
- R_e - cost of equity capital
- R_d - cost of external capital

$$R_e = R_f + \beta(R_M - R_f) = R_f + \beta * \Delta R \quad (2)$$

Re - COST OF EQUITY the CAPM model (Capital Asset Pricing Model) is used to calculate the cost of equity capital. This is the most commonly used method of determining the cost of equity capital. The cost of equity capital is expressed as:

$$R_e = R_f + \beta(R_m - R_f) = R_f + \beta * \Delta R \quad (3)$$

where:

- R_m – average return for industry investors calculated on the basis of reports from the capital market;
- $(R_m - R_f)$ - investment risk premium for the country of investment.

⁷ <https://magnimetrics.com/understanding-the-weighted-average-cost-of-capital-wacc/>

- β - is considered a measure of the systematic risk of an investment (for a given industry sector)
- (Rf) - Risk-free rate, State Treasury bonds are most often considered to be the risk-free rate.

Rdf - th COST OF FOREIGN CAPITAL, COST OF DEBT (RD), is the weighted average interest rate that a company must pay on its debt. The cost of debt can be calculated using the following formula:

$$R = \left(1 + \frac{R_{nom}}{n}\right)^n - 1$$

nominal interest rate – R_{nom} , frequency of interest capitalization in the financial period – n .

It should be noted, that in case where the technology has been implemented and tested on an industrial scale, the technological risk can be considered to be low. In such cases what remains from a technological/technical perspective the for further verification is mainly the market risk - the WACC described above. The results of the LUXEX Project are on TRL 4, which doesn't guarantee a successful implementation - there is a technological risk of not achieving TRL9. This risk results from the nature of R&D work and technology scaling. The technological risk at low TRL levels significantly exceeds the business risk. Therefore, in such cases, a technological risk should be estimated, measured by the discount rate.

It is assumed that the discount rate for the technology is based on the level of TRL (technology readiness level). The base discount rate for a given technology is adjusted according to the nature/data of the market n which the technology is to be implemented.

R&D projects scaling innovative technologies are so-called venture/risk capital projects (in terms of market implementation). The literature (known and used for many years, originating mainly from the US) on venture capital financing explains why the discount rate used in venture capital projects (R&D project) is high. Some of the explanations are quoted below:

- Funds invested by VCs are illiquid (there is no cash inflow from sales) until an initial public offering or acquisition. Amihud and Mendelson (1986) provide evidence that the illiquidity of an asset increases its expected rate of return.
- VC is not a passive investor; (Metrick, 2007; Smith and Smith, 2004). VCs devote a lot of time to each project they invest in: they provide management services, monitoring and privileged access to clients and suppliers in the industry. Therefore, the discount rate reflects not only the systematic risk of the project but also the compensation to the VCs for their time.
- (Damodaran, 2009), indicates that entrepreneurs often present estimates of project cash inflows with an upward trend (overestimated). A higher discount rate corrects this deviation. Common stock returns are important for successful projects because they have net cash inflows.
- Expenditures on a technology development are very important depending on the level of TRL. The **Figure 3** present examples of market risk levels (discount rates) depending on the level of development of a given WNIp/technology.
- According to the publication “Why do venture capitalists use such high discount rates?” Bhagat University of Colorado at Boulder, Boulder, Colorado, USA, The Journal of Risk Finance, Vol. 15 No. 1, 2014, Dependence of risk on the probability of failure/success of project completion is shown in Table 1. For a standard risk r_A of -15%, a VC that estimates the probability of the project's ultimate success between 60 and 40% imposes a discount rate (r^*A) between 42 and 74%.
- According to the publication “Valuing Young, Start-up and Growth Companies: Estimation Issues and Valuation Challenges Aswath” (Damodaran Stern School of Business, New York University, May 2009), **Table 2** below summarizes the venture Capital Target Rate of Return – Stage in Life Cycle.
- According to “The Discount Rate Used by Venture Capital Investors in Each Investment Round”⁸, risk of depending on the technology implementation phases is shown in **Figure 4**.

⁸ <https://flylib.com/books/en/2.488.1.66/1/>

- According to the NUTRIent MANagement and Nutrient Recovery Thematic Network⁹ (project funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 818470) the implementation risk depending on the TRL is shown in Table 3.

Figure 3. Percentage Development vs. TRL.¹⁰

Table 1. Dependence of risk on the probability of failure/success of project completion.

$\frac{p_A}{r_A} \downarrow$	0.30	0.40	0.50	0.60	0.70
0.05	0.92	0.66	0.48	0.36	0.25
0.10	0.96	0.70	0.52	0.39	0.28
0.15	1.00	0.74	0.55	0.42	0.31
0.20	1.05	0.77	0.59	0.45	0.34
0.25	1.09	0.81	0.62	0.48	0.37

Notes: This table provides values of r_A^* , the discount rate used by VCs, where p_A is the probability of eventual success of the project, and r_A is the discount rate implied by the systematic risk of the project (given that it is successful); a risk-free rate of 5 percent is assumed

Table 2. Venture Capital Target rates of Return – Stage in Life Cycle.

Table 2: Venture Capital Target Rates of Return – Stage in Life Cycle

Stage of development	Typical target rates of return
Start up	50-70%
First stage	40-60%
Second stage	35-50%
Bridge / IPO	25-35%

⁹ https://nutriman.net/sites/default/files/2019-01/TRL_IRL_Technology_Readiness_Levels.pdf

¹⁰ <http://www.iceaaonline.com/ready/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/DA05-PPT-Linick-Technology-Readiness-Level.pdf>

Figure 4. The risk of depending on the technology implementation phases.

Table 3. The implementation risk of the depending on the TRL.

Technology Readiness Levels “TRL” – Investment Readiness Levels “IRL”
For objective driven natural and environmental science & technology/product evolutions

	TRL & IRL EVOLUTION schedules and capabilities		Scientific evidence level	
	Status of RTD progress - “RMI” Research Maturity Index	TRL / IRL Implementation factor % / risk %		
EU Community S&T - RTD maturity progress	TRL 1-3 = IDEA = basic principles, technology concept formulated	0-1% / 100%	THESES: theoretical assumptions	
	TRL 4 = technology validated in laboratory	<3% / >97%		
	TRL 5-6 = PILOT technology validated and demonstrated in relevant environment IRL5-6 = validate revenue model & market fit Low RMI operational area	<25% / >90%		
		high technical risk/full commercial risk		
		RTD risk break-even point		
	TRL 7= PROTOTYPE demo in operational environment IRL 7 = prototype viable product	60-75% / 40-70%	Prototype demonstrated	
	TRL8 = FIELD DEMO system complete and qualified IRL 8 = validate value delivery High RMI operational area	75-90% / 15-25%	Industrial validated	
	TRL 9 = actual system proven in operational environment, full scale industrial replication model ready for market competitive commercial deployment. IRL 9 = identify and validate metrics	95-99% / 1-5%	Market validated commercial replication	
	Industrialized and market competitive commercialized innovation	97-99% / 1-5%	Commercial replicated	

✓ **The TRL** (also known as Technology Readiness Assessment “TRA”) is based on the EU Commission Decision C(2014)4995 and US official methods since 1980’s (NASA, DoD, ESA, European Commission since 2014 in the H2020, ISO 16290:2013 standard).
 ✓ **The IRL** is based on the OECD (The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) and other large financial institutions methods. IRL is an evidence based demonstration to investors, that there’s a repeatable and scalable business model.

Summarizing the discount risk data, the implementation of R&D project result is connected with a discount risk related to the level of technology (it increases as the TRL levels decrease) and typical business risk. Estimating the level of discount risk is very important in the process of valuating/pricing the technology, e.g. for the purpose of selling rights to the technology or licensing rights to the technology (commercialization from science to industry). At low TRLs, technological discount risk prevails, and for mature technologies there is only typical business risk in a given market.

4.1 Discount risk for the Technology at present time

Based on Table 2 the discount risk is estimated at 30-40%, because the Technology components are known and based on known phenomena. They are not just proven on a quarter-technical (and technical) scale as a whole. The market is known. So, we have: new product, new manufacturing process, known market. It is also assumed that there are no exclusive rights (other patents) that are an obstacle to the Technology implementation.

4.2 Discount risk for the Technology at higher TRL levels (future TRL = 8, TRL = 9)

As shown above, for technologies at TRL>8 it can be assumed that WACC is calculated according to the formula:

$$WACC = f_e * R_e + f_d R_d(1 - T_c)$$

where:

- f_e - is the percentage (%) share of the cost of equity in the investment
- f_d - is the percentage (%) share of the cost of external capital in the investment
- T_c - income tax for the company
- R_e - cost of equity capital
- R_d - cost of external capital

It has been assumed that the implementation of the Technology (e.g. by the license purchaser) would not be supported by external capital, therefore, f_d is the percentage (%) share of the cost of external capital in the investment and it equals to 0%. Therefore, the formula takes the form:

$$WACC = f_e * R_e = R_e = R_f + \beta(R_m - R_f) = R_f + \beta * \Delta R$$

where

- β - is considered as a measure of the systematic risk of an investment (for given industry sector). For the industry correlated to the LUXWEX Project according to the Damodaran database¹¹ :

Industry Name	Number of firms	β
Environmental & Waste Services	52	0,89

The above illustrates the level of β in the Environmental & Waste Services industry. For other industries we have:

- Electronics (General) $\beta=1,15$
- Bank (Money Center) $\beta=0,36$
- Drugs (Biotechnology) $\beta=1,13$
- Drugs (Pharmaceutical) $\beta=0,90$

- R_f – interest rate for investments considered risk-free. For the Polish market $R_f = 6.8^{12} = 10$ -year treasury bonds. It was assumed as a 10-years investment return period
- $\Delta R = (R_m - R_f)$ - investment risk premium for the country of investment. According to Damodaran database premium for the business market in Poland up to 1.24^{13}

The calculation:

$$WACC = R_f + \beta * \Delta R = 6.8 + 0,89 * 1,24 = 7,9\% \sim 8\% \text{ for implementation in the Polish market.}$$

Analogously for the **German market**:

$$R_f = 2,52^{14}$$

$$\Delta R(R_m - R_f) = 0,0 \%$$

$$WACC = R_f + \beta * \Delta R = 2,52 + 0,89 * 0,0 = 2,52\% \sim 2,5\%$$

Analogously for the **Italian market**:

$$R_f = 3,84^{15}$$

¹¹ <https://pages.stern.nyu.edu/~adamodar/> at 05.2024y.

¹² <https://www.obligacjieskarbowe.pl/oferta/>, na dzień 28/04/2020

¹³ <https://pages.stern.nyu.edu/~adamodar/>, na dzień 28/04/2020

¹⁴ <https://pl.investing.com/rates-bonds/germany-10-year-bond-yield>

¹⁵ <https://pl.investing.com/rates-bonds/italy-10-year-bond-yield>

$$\Delta R = (R_m - R_f) = 3,21\%$$

$$WACC = R_f + \beta * \Delta R = 3,84 + 0,89 * 3,21 = 6,69\% \sim 7\%$$

Analogously for the **Austrian market**:

$$R_f = 4,26^{16}$$

$$\Delta R = (R_m - R_f) = 0.58\%$$

$$WACC = R_f + \beta * \Delta R = 4,26 + 0,89 * 0,58 = 4,7\% \sim 5\%$$

Summary of the estimation of the discount risk of technology (technology correlated to the LUWEX Project) implementation (for TRL>8) in the countries of the LUWEX Project’s consortium members is shown in Table 4. The lower discount risks. the better for the implementation success of the Technology.

Table 4. Summary of the risks of Technology implementation (for TRL>8) in the countries of the LUWEX Project’s consortium members.

Country	WACC [%]
Poland	8%
Italy	7%
Austria	5%
Germany	2,5%

¹⁶ <https://pl.investing.com/rates-bonds/australia-10-year-bond-yield>

5 CAPEX

Capex - Capital expenditure or capital expense (abbreviated capex, CAPEX, or CapEx) is the amount that an organization or corporate entity spends to buy, maintain, or improve its fixed assets, such as buildings, vehicles, equipment or land. It is considered a capital expenditure when the asset is newly purchased or when money is used towards extending the useful life of an existing asset¹⁷.

Total budget of LUWEX is € 1.499.008,25. The cost of work of TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET BRAUNSCHWEIG related to the module for obtaining water from the regolith will be ignored for the further analysis as the negligible for this approach. We can also assume that the 80% of the remaining costs are the costs of labour (not including the issue of obtaining water from the regolith). Thus, we can assume that the cost of R&D works for the SWOT analysis including the fact of early application (TRL4) is around 1 million €.

Regarding the market data, we can base our calculations on the construction of a technical, but experimental, installation for purifying water from pharmaceuticals through ozonation - a project of Wodociagi Jaworzno Sp. z o.o. [polish company]. The cost of this project was approximately €4 million (2022).

Based on the data above and our experience the amount of approximately 4 million Euro should be sufficient to build the installation (in container buildings, which will allow for an easy transportation and testing) to achieve the TRL 8. Of course, it strongly depends on the cost of raw materials, which [at present time] changes quite quickly.

Generally, CAPEX is currently difficult to estimate due to the low TRL. As described in the recommendations part, first of all, tests should be carried out on a quarter-scale, after which it should be possible to estimate CAPEX for the implementing company. CAPEX also depends on the size of the installation and its assumed performance, which can be estimated at the stage of developing a feasibility study and technical assumptions.

¹⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Capital_expenditure.

6 Water resources problem

The LUWEX Project’s results (at terrestrial applications) has three modules:

- water purification module
- water quality monitoring module
- storage module

These modules could be the answer to the problems of water on the earth. Water is extremely important for industry and humans. Water available worldwide covers 75% of the earth's surface and the available hydrosphere is up to 1.4 billion/km². However, fresh water constitutes only 3% of all available water resources.

According to the data from the World Resources Institute¹⁸ (WRI), 36 countries around the world are exposed to water deficits (water stress by Country 2040 is shown in **Figure 5**). Generally, most of them are Asian and African countries, water problem also occurs on many islands from North or South America. According to forecasts, global water demand is expected to increase significantly in the coming decades. This rise in demand will be driven not only by the growth of the world's population but also by increased consumption and the migration of rural inhabitants to cities, which will further strain urban resources.

The United Nations forecasts that by 2050 the world population will increase to 9.3 billion with 6.3 billion people living in urban areas. Globally,¹⁹ areas with water deficit are primarily located in tropical and subtropical climate zones, as well as in dry subequatorial climate zones and the interior of continents, far from oceans.

Water Stress by Country: 2040

NOTE: Projections are based on a business-as-usual scenario using SSP2 and RCP8.5.

For more: ow.ly/RiWop

 WORLD RESOURCES INSTITUTE

Figure 5. Water stress by Country 2040²⁰

¹⁸ <https://www.wri.org/>

¹⁹ <https://zpe.gov.pl/a/obszary-nadmiaru-i-niedoboru-wody-na-swiecie/DMcmqVzvD>

²⁰ World Resources Institute – WRI

Figure 6. Level of water stress (water scarcity) – water abstraction in relation to water resources (%).²¹

The European Union is increasingly focusing on the protection of water resources. It has issued a document, the "Plan for the protection of European water resources" aimed at ensuring the availability of good quality water for all inhabitants. According to the document, the level of freshwater resources per capita in France, Spain, Germany, Poland, Great Britain and Italy is alarmingly low. In recent years the situation has become critical also in Malta, Cyprus, the Czech Republic and Poland.²²

Renewable freshwater resources are shown in Figure 7. In almost half of the EU countries, fresh water resources are alarmingly low (below 3,000 m³ per person), including Poland, Malta, Cyprus and the Czech Republic, where the level is below the level of water security²³.

Figure 7. Renewable freshwater resources (in thousand m³ per capita, annual averages over 20 years)²⁴

²¹ 2020 report, , Poland on the path to sustainable development, <https://raportsdg.stat.gov.pl/2020/cel6.html>

²² https://inzynieria.com/wodkan/analizy_i_komentarze/51374,kraje-najbardziej-zagrozone-deficytem-wody

²³ according to the UN, the limit below which a country is considered at risk of such water shortage is 1.7 thousand m³ per inhabitant

²⁴ <https://raportsdg.stat.gov.pl/2020/cel6.html>

6.1 Water in industry

It should be noted that the most water-intensive industries are:^{25,26}

- Agriculture (including water to irrigate crop fields)
- Textile/Fashion industry
- Energy industry
- Meat industry
- Beverage industry
- Construction, mining, metallurgical industries
- Car industries
- Pulp and paper
- Chemical

According to the EEA Water Use Index, economic activities in Europe use on average around 243,000 cubic hectometres of water per year. Even though most of this water (over 140,000 cubic hectometres) is returned to the environment, it often contains contaminants or dirt, including hazardous chemicals.²⁷ The changes in water consumption in the world are shown in **Figure 8**.

Figure 8. Changes in water consumption around the World. ²⁸

- Globally agriculture is one of the largest consumers of water, accounting for approximately 70% of all freshwater withdrawals.²⁹ Agriculture is also the largest water user in Europe - it uses around 40% of the total amount of water used annually³⁰.
- The textile/ fashion industry is one of the most water-intensive industries worldwide. For example, according to the Water Footprint Network creating a single pair of jeans requires about 2,866 gallons of water.³¹
- Mining and manufacturing account for 18% of water use and households account for approximately 12% of water use. On average, 144 litres of water per person per day are supplied to European households.

²⁵ <https://zpe.gov.pl/a/przeczytaj/DRL3IUM2a>

²⁶ <https://2030.builders/world-water-day/>

²⁷ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/pl/sygna142y/sygnaly-2018/artykuly/zuzycie-wody-w-europie-2014>

²⁸ <https://zpe.gov.pl/a/obszary-nadmiaru-i-niedoboru-wody-na-swiecie/DMcmqVzVD>

²⁹ <https://www.worldexcellence.com/water-consumption-rates-which-industries-use-the-most/>

³⁰ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/pl/sygna142y/sygnaly-2018/artykuly/zuzycie-wody-w-europie-2014>

³¹ <https://www.thomasnet.com/insights/which-industries-use-the-most-water/>

- In different regions, different sectors may have the highest water consumption. Overall, agriculture is the largest user of water in Southern Europe, while cooling for energy production exerts the greatest pressure on water resources in Western and Eastern Europe. The manufacturing industry is the largest user of water in Northern Europe. Examples of water use - according to the Water Footprint Network:
- It takes between 680 and 1241 litres to produce a 2-litre bottle of soda. It takes 75 litres of water to make a pint of beer It takes 140 litres of water to produce the ingredients to make a single cup of coffee It takes a staggering 147 631 litres to produce the average domestic vehicle. In the automotive industry, major water use occurs in³²:
 - Surface treatment and coating
 - Paint spray booths
 - Washing/rinsing/hosing
 - Cooling
 - Air conditioning systems^{33,34}.
- The energy industry is another major consumer of water, with water used for cooling purposes in thermal power generation and for hydraulic fracturing in oil and natural gas extraction. Power plants that use cooling towers, common in nuclear and fossil fuel power generation, can consume vast amounts of water. The oil and gas industry also require significant amounts of water for hydraulic fracturing, or fracking, to extract oil and gas from shale formations.³⁵ Energy production uses approximately 28% of annual water consumption. Water is mainly used for cooling in nuclear and fossil fuel.³⁶

6.2 Water problems created by pharmaceutical industry

According to the industry article "Pharmaceuticals in wastewater³⁷" - "Economic development and the related pressure, constant stress in everyday life, have made functioning without pharmaceuticals seem impossible for many people. The search for an effective method using activated sludge microorganisms to combat the growing wave of drug consumption is a challenge for scientists from all over the world."

The article "Drug residues in water and sewage are an increasing problem. Not only producers will pay³⁸" presents some data/trends regarding drugs in wastewater:

- Research in many countries, including Poland, confirms the presence of over 80 pharmaceuticals in the aquatic environment. Some of them are even detected in treated drinking water.
- The European Union plans to tighten regulations regarding the removal of these types of contaminants from water and sewage networks.
- Individual EU member states are also trying to properly address the problem. For example, the Dutch government does not rule out requiring pharmaceutical companies to pay for the removal of pharmaceutical residues from wastewater.

³² <https://smarterbusiness.co.uk/blogs/the-top-5-industries-that-consume-the-most-water/>

³³ <https://www.money.pl/gospodarka/paradoks-bialego-zlota-lit-jest-niezbedny-do-produkcji-elektrykow-6979652225935872a.html>

³⁴ <https://forsal.pl/biznes/energetyka/artykuly/8328526,baterie-litowo-jonowe-recykling-akumulatory-problem.html>

³⁵ <https://www.worldexcellence.com/water-consumption-rates-which-industries-use-the-most/>

³⁶ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/pl/sygna142y/sygnaly-2018/artykuly/zuzycie-wody-w-europie-2014>.

³⁷ <https://www.kierunekwodkan.pl/artykul,5379,farmaceutyki-w-sciekach.html>

³⁸ <https://www.portalsamorzadowy.pl/gospodarka-komunalna/resztki-lekow-w-wodzie-i-sciekach-coraz-wiekszym-problemem-zaplaca-nie-tylko-producenci,455265.html>

7 The Market

7.1 Water purification methods - overview

The main technologies used in water treatment:

- **Coagulation / Flocculation**
- **Filtration**
 - including nanophotonic, nanographene membrane filtration, nanostructured polymer materials, ceramic, sand filters
 - bio-based membrane
 - membrane purification technologies focused on increasing the permeability coefficient to enhance efficiency (cost reduction)
 - membrane filtration consumes a lot of energy, partly due to the pump system
 - membrane fouling (e.g. by inorganic, and organic matter) decreases performance and quality
- **Disinfection** - distillation consumes a lot of energy
- **Adsorption**

At domestic applications ultraviolet (UV) and reverse osmosis (RO) technologies have 90% of the market.

The goal of water purification is to remove:

- toxins and heavy metals including lead, arsenic, fluoride, cadmium
- salt from seawater In Europe, Spain is the leading producer of desalinated water, producing 3,8 million m³/per day.
- Recently trends include:
 - elimination of waterborne Epidemics (viruses, and pathogenic bacteria, hormones, contraceptives)
 - Use of AI technologies and intelligent sensors (machine learning)

According to the Department of Health and Human Services (HHS)³⁹ water treatment steps include:

- **Coagulation** - often the first step in water treatment. During coagulation, chemicals with a positive charge are added to the water. The positive charge neutralizes the negative charge of dirt and other dissolved particles in the water. When this occurs, the particles bind with the chemicals to form slightly larger particles. Common chemicals used in this step include specific types of salts, aluminum, or iron.
- **Flocculation** – following the coagulation step. Flocculation is the gentle mixing of the water to form larger, heavier particles called flocs. Often, water treatment plants add additional chemicals during this step to help the flocs form.
- **Sedimentation** - one of the steps water treatment plants use to separate out solids from the water. During sedimentation, flocs settle to the bottom of the water because they are heavier than the water.
- **Filtration** - Once the flocs have settled to the bottom of the water, the clear water on top is filtered to separate additional solids from the water. During filtration, the clear water passes through filters that have different pore sizes and are made of different materials (such as sand, gravel, and charcoal). These filters remove dissolved particles and germs, such as dust, chemicals, parasites, bacteria, and viruses. Activated carbon filters also remove any bad odours. Reverse osmosis is another filtration method that removes additional particles from water. Water treatment plants often use reverse osmosis when treating recycled water (also called reused water) or salt water for drinking.
- **Disinfection** - after the water has been filtered, water treatment plants may add one or more chemical disinfectants (such as chlorine, chloramine, or chlorine dioxide) to kill any remaining parasites, bacteria, or viruses. To help keep the water safe as it travels to homes and businesses, water treatment plants will make sure the water has low levels of the chemical disinfectant when it leaves the

³⁹ <https://www.cdc.gov/>

treatment plant. This residual disinfectant continues to kill germs that may be present in the pipes between the water treatment plant and the taps in homes and businesses.

In addition to or instead of adding chlorine, chloramine, or chlorine dioxide, water treatment plants can also disinfect water using ultraviolet (UV) light or ozone. UV light and ozone effectively disinfect water at the treatment plant, although they do not continue to kill germs as the water travels through the pipes between the treatment plant and the tap.⁴⁰

7.2 The market in numbers

- According to Meticulous Research the value of the European water and wastewater treatment market will grow by an average of 4% per year until it exceeds USD 170 billion by 2030.⁴¹
- According to Precedence Research, the global water purifier market is poised for significant growth over the next decade. The value of the market was at \$43.2 billion in 2022 and it will grow to \$120.38 billion by 2032 - CAGR of 10.79%. A recent study by the U.S. Geological Survey estimates that at least 45% of America's tap water contains polyfluorinated alkyl substances (PFAS). PFAS are synthetic chemicals, also known as "forever chemicals," because they don't break down in the environment or in the human body. PFAS are commonly found in consumer products such as cleaning products, non-stick cookware and personal care products such as shampoo, dental floss and nail polish.⁴²
- According to Fortune Business Insights the global water purifier market size was \$30.62 billion in 2022 and is projected to grow from \$33.65 billion in 2023 to \$54.48 billion by 2030, at a CAGR of 7.6%.⁴³
- According to Markets & Data⁴⁴ the demand for efficient water filtration technologies has become critical. The global water purifier market is forecasted to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 11.82% from 2023 to 2030. Water purifiers are essential appliances in homes, workplaces, various industries, and enterprises worldwide since they are made to remove pollutants and contaminants from water sources. The market has grown due to technological developments, increasing awareness of waterborne disease, and government programs promoting water safety. The market is estimated to reach USD 84.11 billion by 2030 from USD 34.41 billion in 2022⁴⁵ driven by the proliferation of manufacturing enterprises, marketing practices, raising hygiene concerns, and innovations in water purification products.

7.3 Key players in the global water purification market

- 3M Company
- Midea Group Co., Ltd.
- Culligan International Company
- Unilever PLC
- Coway Co., Ltd.
- O. Smith Corporation
- DuPont de Nemours, Inc
- Kent RO Systems Ltd.

⁴⁰ quote from https://www.cdc.gov/healthywater/drinking/public/water_treatment.html

⁴¹ <https://automatykab2b.pl/gospodarka/57722-europejski-rynek-uzdatniania-wody-i-oczyszczania-sciekow>

⁴² <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbesbusinesscouncil/2023/11/15/growth-trends-in-the-water-purification-industry/?sh=2b1266467a1c>

⁴³ <https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/water-purifier-market-103118>

⁴⁴ <https://www.marketsanddata.com/industry-reports/water-purifier-market>

⁴⁵ The global water purifier market consists of various water purification technologies, including reverse osmosis (RO) purifiers, ultraviolet (UV) purifiers, gravity-based purifiers, activated carbon purifiers and many more. Industrial water filters help eliminate impurities from water. Removing suspended particulates or creating filtered water are two procedures that use various water filters. Cartridge, Bag, Basket Filters, and Self-cleaning filters are widely used in multiple industries. Typical industrial water treatment techniques include Softening, Nanofiltration, Filtration, Reverse osmosis, Ion exchange, and dealkalization.

- Eureka Forbes Ltd
- Panasonic Corporation
- LG Corporation
- Pentair PLC
- BLUEWATER SWEDEN AB

Bluewater technology removes up to 99.99% of microplastics from tap water. “Studies conducted by Bluewater at its research lab in the Royal Institute of Technology (KTH) have shown that the company's water purifier technology can remove up to 99.99% of health threatening microplastics and chemicals such as toxic perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) from tap water”.⁴⁶

" The long-term implications for human health of ingesting microplastics and the chemicals in them remains something of a black hole due to lack of dedicated research," said Bluewater senior research scientist Ahmed Fawzy. In March 2022, microplastics were found in the blood samples of 22 anonymous donors by researchers at Vrije University in Amsterdam; the most common plastic found was polyethylene terephthalate (PET), used to create water bottles.”⁴⁷

B) “Patented Bluewater SuperiorOsmosis™ technology turns municipal, well or brackish water into pure, delicious-tasting water. Efficient and more effective than other reverse osmosis systems, it circulates water, pushing it through a large semipermeable, self-cleaning membrane. A big reason for the best outcome is the larger membrane area. The result is purified water, free from contaminants, such as toxins, heavy metals, bacteria and pharmaceuticals.”⁴⁸

- **NEW MILLENNIUM CONCEPTS, LTD.**

New Millennium Concepts, Ltd. (NMCL) is the manufacturer of Berkey® line of gravity-fed water filtration systems, the industry gold standard for performance and value.⁴⁹

- **AQUISENSE TECHNOLOGIES.**

The company uses UV-C LED disinfection which utilizes light to damage the DNA of pathogens. “This technology offers a variety of new benefits when compared to conventional UV purification. Similar to how visible LEDs effected the display market, Aquisense Technologies believes UV-C LEDs will have a lasting effect on how we disinfect water, surfaces and air.”⁵⁰

Regarding the membrane technologies:

- **Inosep⁵¹**

“Based out of South Korea, Inosep is pushing the boundaries of polymer membrane technology. Their suite includes a range of membranes tailored for specific purification requirements – be it microfiltration, ultrafiltration, nanofiltration, or the much-acclaimed reverse osmosis (RO). (...) Leveraging polymer materials like polyamide, polyethylene, and cellulose acetate, they ensure their membranes are adept for diverse applications”⁵²

⁴⁶ <https://www.bluewatergroup.com/en-us/press-coverage/bluewater-technology-removes-up-to-99-99-of-microplastics-from-tap-water>

⁴⁷ <https://africanreview.com/manufacturing/water-a-environment/bluewater-technology-removes-up-to-99-99-of-microplastics-from-tap-water>

⁴⁸ https://www-bluewatergroup-com.translate.goog/en-us/blog/what-is-great-about-superiorosmosis?_x_tr_sl=en&_x_tr_tl=pl&_x_tr_hl=pl&_x_tr_pto=wapp

⁴⁹ <https://www.berkeywater.com/company/>

⁵⁰ <https://aquisense.com/uv-c-led-technology/>

⁵¹ <https://www.innosep.co.th/>

⁵² a quote from <https://ticonsultants.com/6-innovations-transforming-the-water-treatment-industry/>

- **Eique**

Biomimetic membranes⁵³ “Earthy is carving a niche for itself with its unique biomimetic membranes. Their technology, aptly named “Aquaporin Inside”, draws inspiration from nature. Mimicking the external structure of a cell, the membrane incorporates aquaporin proteins, renowned for their water transportation efficiency in living cells.”⁵⁴

Regarding the carbon-based purification:

- **Bygen**⁵⁵

“Bygen Activated is revolutionizing the production of activated carbon. Their innovative approach hinges on a low-temperature activation (LTA) process. Not only is this process self-sustaining, but it also circumvents the need for continuous heating.”⁵⁶

- **Glanris**⁵⁷

“Glanris is propelling carbon-based purification to new heights. Their flagship offering—a biocarbon media crafted from rice husks—stands out as a paragon of eco-friendly water treatment solutions. This biocarbon media is not just adept at removing organic contaminants but also showcases efficiency against metal impurities.”

Regarding the bio-based water remediation:

- **Advanced Bacterial Sciences (ABS)**⁵⁸. “Nestled in the UK, ABS is making monumental strides in bacterial-based water treatments. Their flagship product, ALGAEZAP 1, embodies their vision. Infused with slow-release bacteria, it efficiently combats excess nutrients and sludge in water bodies, warding off detrimental phenomena like algal blooms and eutrophication.”⁵⁹

- **Duckweed Biotech**⁶⁰.

“Hailing from the US, Duckweed Biotech is carving a unique niche with its phytoremediation solutions. At the heart of their technology lies a proprietary hydroponics system, tailored for water purification and greenhouse gas sequestration. Their modus operandi harnesses phytoremediation to cleanse nutrient-laden runoff water and agricultural wastewater.”⁶¹

Regarding the nanofiltration:

- **NematiQ**⁶²

“A ground-breaking venture from Australia, NematiQ is championing the cause of graphene nanofiltration membranes. Harnessing a patented high-speed layer-by-layer manufacturing technique, the start-up creates membranes that are a marvel in both structure and function. These graphene-infused membranes boast of high permeability, ensuring swift passage of water and specific salts. Meanwhile, their nuanced molecular weight cut-off ensures larger undesirable entities—ranging from organic contaminants, colours, to even pathogens like bacteria and viruses—are systematically rejected.”⁶³

- **Peore**⁶⁴

“Venturing from India, Peore offers a refreshing take on nanofiltration. Their centrepiece is an intelligently designed semi-permeable membrane, boasting a pore size of 0.001 microns—just a tad larger than conven-

⁵³ <https://earthy.care/water-membranes/>

⁵⁴ a quote from <https://ttconsultants.com/6-innovations-transforming-the-water-treatment-industry/>

⁵⁵ <https://www.bygen.com.au/>

⁵⁶ a quote from <https://ttconsultants.com/6-innovations-transforming-the-water-treatment-industry/>

⁵⁷ <https://www.glanris.com/>

⁵⁸ <https://abs.eco/>

⁵⁹ a quote from <https://ttconsultants.com/6-innovations-transforming-the-water-treatment-industry/>

⁶⁰ <https://duckweed.bio/>

⁶¹ a quote from <https://ttconsultants.com/6-innovations-transforming-the-water-treatment-industry/>

⁶² <https://www.nematiq.com/>

⁶³ a quote from <https://ttconsultants.com/6-innovations-transforming-the-water-treatment-industry/>

⁶⁴ <https://www.leduv-c.co.uk/>

tional reverse osmosis membranes. (...) Complementing their nanofiltration technology is their Tru-UV system. Here, water is channelled through quartz glass within a high-reflectivity chamber, ensuring maximum UV exposure and, in turn, deactivating a spectrum of pathogens”⁶⁵

Regarding the water disinfection solutions:

- **LED UV-C Systems**⁶⁶

“Anchored in the UK, this start-up is elevating the domain of UV disinfection. Their flagship product, PearlAqua Micro, encapsulates their vision—a compact UV disinfection system that promises instantaneous germicidal intensity right at start-up and boasts an impressive lamp lifespan of up to 10,000 hours. Their UV AOP stands as a testament to their commitment to sustainable purification. By synergizing LED-produced UV photons with hydrogen peroxide, it produces hydroxyl radicals that are adept at neutralizing water contaminants⁶⁷”

- **Algaesys**⁶⁸

“Algaesys introduces a novel paradigm—water treatment leveraging colonized phototrophic biomass. Their system is comprehensive in its purification, targeting a range of contaminants from nitrogen and phosphorus to micro-plastics and persistent organics.⁶⁹”

⁶⁵ a quote from <https://ttconsultants.com/6-innovations-transforming-the-water-treatment-industry/>

⁶⁶ <https://www.peore.in/>

⁶⁷ a quote from <https://ttconsultants.com/6-innovations-transforming-the-water-treatment-industry/>

⁶⁸ <https://www.algaesys.earth/>

⁶⁹ a quote from <https://ttconsultants.com/6-innovations-transforming-the-water-treatment-industry/>

8 Innovations in water purification systems developed by universities

Below some examples of water purification systems developed by universities are presented:

1. **Hydrophobic nanostructured wood membrane for thermally efficient distillation**⁷⁰ from the University of Maryland, College Park, Princeton University. The scientists develop “a first robust MD membrane directly fabricated from sustainable wood material. The hydrophobic nanowood membrane has high porosity ($89 \pm 3\%$) and hierarchical pore structure with a wide pore size distribution of crystalline cellulose nanofibrils and xylem vessels and lumina (channels) that facilitate water vapor transportation. The thermal conductivity was extremely low in the transverse direction, which reduces conductive heat transport. However, high thermal conductivity along the fibre enables efficient thermal dissipation along the axial direction. As a result, the membrane demonstrates excellent intrinsic vapor permeability ($1.44 \pm 0.09 \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$) and thermal efficiency ($\sim 70\%$ at 60°C). The properties of thermal efficiency, water flux, scalability, and sustainability make nanowood highly desirable for MD applications.”
2. **Precise nanofiltration in a fouling-resistant self-assembled membrane** with water-continuous transport pathways⁷¹ developed by scientists from Center for Advanced Low-dimension Materials, State Key Laboratory for Modification of Chemical Fibers and Polymer Materials, Donghua University, Shanghai 201620, China., Department of Chemical and Environmental Engineering, Yale University, New Haven, CT 06511, USA, Department of Chemical and Biomolecular Engineering, University of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia, PA 19104, USA, ESPCI Paris, 10 Rue Vauquelin, 75005 Paris, France, Department of Chemistry, Graduate School of Science, Tohoku University, 6-3 Aoba, Aramaki, Aoba-Ku, Sendai, Japan.

“Their developed membranes show size selectivity at the 1- to 2-nm length scale and water permeabilities of $\sim 10 \text{ litres m}^{-2} \text{ hour}^{-1} \text{ bar}^{-1} \mu\text{m}$. Moreover, the membranes display excellent antimicrobial properties due to the quaternary ammonium groups on the nanofibril surfaces. These results represent a breakthrough for the potential use of polymerized lyotropic mesophase membranes in practical water purification applications.”⁷²

3. **University of Texas. Water Purification Breakthrough Uses Sunlight and Hydrogels.** “The ability to create clean, safe drinking water using only natural levels of sunlight and inexpensive gel technology could be at hand, thanks to an innovation in water purification.”⁷³ “Led by Guihua Yu, associate professor of materials science and mechanical engineering at The University of Texas at Austin, a research team in UT Austin’s Cockrell School of Engineering has developed a cost-effective and compact technology using combined gel-polymer hybrid materials. Possessing both hydrophilic (attraction to water) qualities and semiconducting (solar-adsorbing) properties, these “hydrogels” (networks of polymer chains known for their high-water absorbency) enable the production of clean, safe drinking water from any source, whether it’s from the oceans or contaminated supplies.”

4. Researchers at Rice University’s Laboratory for Nanophotonics (LANP).

Solar Desalination System Delivers High Energy Output. “By adding inexpensive plastic lenses, Rice University’s Laboratory for Nanophotonics boosted the efficiency of their solar-powered desalination system. There are 16,000 desalination plants operating around the world today. These plants produce 3 billion cubic feet of fresh water. The industry continues to grow and new methods will be needed to create a more efficient process. Researchers at Rice University’s Laboratory for Nanophotonics (LANP) proved that they could boost the efficiency of their solar-powered desalination system by more than 50 percent under ambient solar illumination without using any bulky solar concentrators”⁷⁴.

⁷⁰https://www.researchgate.net/publication/334900016_Hydrophobic_nanostructured_wood_membrane_for_thermally_efficient_distillation

⁷¹ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31448326/#full-view-affiliation-1>

⁷² <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31448326/#full-view-affiliation-1>

⁷³ <https://news.utexas.edu/2018/04/03/water-purification-breakthrough-uses-sunlight-and-hydrogels/>

⁷⁴ <https://www.asme.org/topics-resources/content/solar-desalination-system-delivers-high-energy-output>

5. **Graphene from Lodz University of Technology in water treatment technology.** “Researchers from the Institute of Materials Science and Engineering at Lodz University of Technology have developed an innovative technology to produce graphene electrodes for water treatment. Thanks to the use of a new coating they have obtained electrodes that are much more durable in use and, what is most important, much cheaper.”⁷⁵
6. The scientists of Taltech are developing a **technology for water purification by electric discharges**⁷⁶ at the Department of Material and Environmental Technology, the Laboratory of Environmental Technology.

“As a result of the last five years of research, our research team has developed a reliable novel, plasma water treatment by electrical discharge method. In this method, water is showered between electrodes with discharge pulses of voltage pulse amplitude of 18–20 kV. By this method we can produce drinking water as suitable for consumption as the one produced by ozonation. No carcinogens are produced and the process is three times less expensive,” says Sergei Preis.⁷⁷

7. **Researchers pioneer new solar steam method for water purification** at Pritzker School of Molecular Engineering (PME) and Argonne National Laboratory. “Scientists and engineers were part of a team that developed a new method of solar steam generation that could help bring this technology into the real world.” “Researchers have already used various photothermal materials, which convert light to heat, for solar steam generation, such as carbon materials, plasmonic metals, and semiconductors. But many of these options have relatively low efficiency, among other challenges. (...) What sets Xia’s method apart is the use of a porphyrin covalent organic framework (POF). POFs, a newly discovered class of materials, have the advantage of growing uniformly on the surface of a variety of materials with different levels of porosity, and they show high performance for water evaporation. POFs also have unique light-harvesting characteristics beneficial for new application.”⁷⁸

⁷⁵ <https://p.lodz.pl/en/about-tul/news/graphene-lodz-university-technology-water-treatment-technology>

⁷⁶ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0304388618303358>

⁷⁷ <https://taltech.ee/en/news/scientists-taltech-are-developing-technology-water-purification-electric-discharges>

⁷⁸ <https://pme.uchicago.edu/news/researchers-pioneer-new-solar-steam-method-water-purification>

9 Guidelines and Regulations

The data on the UE guidelines and regulatory trends are summarized below. In the document COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE EUROPEAN COUNCIL, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS⁷⁹, includes:

- In Article 8c of the Priority Substances Directive (Directive 2008/105/EC as amended by Directive 2013/39/EU) the European Commission is required to propose a strategic approach to water pollution by pharmaceutical substances.
- Residues of several pharmaceutical substances were found across the EU in surface and groundwater, soil and animal tissues, with concentrations varying depending on the substance and the nature and proximity of their sources. Some painkillers, antimicrobials, antidepressants, contraceptives and antiparasitic are common. Traces of some pharmaceutical substances were also found in drinking water
- In October 2022, the European Commission adopted a proposal to revise the list of priority substances in surface waters. It is proposed to add 25 substances, including a standard for pesticides in general. The proposed substances pose well-documented threats to nature and human health. These include: PFAS - a large group of "forever chemicals" used in kitchenware, clothing and furniture, fire-fighting foams and personal care products; assortment of pesticides; bisphenol A, a plasticizer and component of plastic packaging; a range of pharmaceuticals used as painkillers, anticonvulsants or antibiotics.
- According to the European Commission, reducing the waste of pharmaceutical substances and their proper disposal can help reduce risks to the environment. In some places, the use of advanced wastewater treatment technologies may be appropriate. It is particularly necessary to control sources of diffuse emissions from livestock farming.
- Actions that the European Commission will undertake regarding urban waste water treatment:
 - application of EU programs to invest in technologies to improve the efficiency of removal of pharmaceutical substances (and antimicrobial resistance genes);
 - assessment, as part of a study in support of the assessment of existing municipal wastewater treatment regulations, whether pharmaceutical emissions are sufficiently controlled and examination of the feasibility of upgrading selected urban wastewater treatment plants with more advanced treatment technologies;
- Actions that the European Commission will undertake to expand environmental monitoring:
 - include additional, potentially relevant pharmaceutical substances, such as cytotoxic pharmaceuticals and X-ray contrast agents, in the review of the watch list for surface waters under the Water Framework Directive, and consider the possibility of monitoring antimicrobial-resistant microorganisms and antimicrobial resistance genes;

⁷⁹ [chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:fc930f14-d7ae-11ec-a95f-01aa75ed71a1.0001.02/DOC_1&format=PDF](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:fc930f14-d7ae-11ec-a95f-01aa75ed71a1.0001.02/DOC_1&format=PDF)

10 Potential spin-off

Definition of spin-offs - an enterprise founded by at least one scientist, scientific or research institution or a student or graduate for the purpose of commercializing innovative ideas or technologies, usually dependent in some way on the parent organization (e.g. by IP licencing). The spin-off shareholder may also be a special purpose vehicle of the university or an enterprise. In the initial phase of operation (usually first 5 years) a spin-off is a start-up.

Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden. shows the standard funding options for start-ups. In the case of LUXEX Project the idea is a know-how (applications on the earth) developed at the LUXEX Project.

Figure 9. Start-up funding works.⁸⁰

Resources necessary to establish a spin-off/start-up:

1. Shareholder– scientists from the LUXEX Project. A basic question which arises here is: Do scientists (at least one) from the scientific LUXEX team want to start a company? Whether they have time and energy to run a business. Let's assume that yes, so we can proceed to the next steps.

⁸⁰ <https://www.wamda.com/2013/10/startup-idea-to-ipo-infographic>

2. Technology. Technology is a core of a start-up. The LUXWEX Consortium must write down the know-how of the LUXWEX Project regarding the applications on the earth. Thus, it can be transferred to a start-up under the IP transfer agreement. A representative of the LUXWEX Consortium will sign the IP transfer agreement (or all consortium members will do it), so their full rights to the results are assured.

An IP transfer agreement – an agreement between the LUXWEX Consortium and a start-up. A standard is a licencing agreement (possibly exclusive, non-exclusive, limited) with an initial fee, an annual fee and a success fee. The exact financial conditions are negotiated by the Consortium (usually by a TTO from the scientific units or an R&D department of a company) with a start-up.

3. Start-up team. Other people (who don't have to be the shareholders of a start-up but cooperate with it) like: manager, technology broker (including a person responsible for an intellectual and legal property protection) and scientists helping to develop the technology to higher levels of TRL.

The team is very important. It often happens that a great technology is lost because the team wasn't ready for a market activity. Generally, it should be noted that 90% of innovative (start 'up) businesses fail (data for the USA) - 9 out of 10 start-ups don't survive the first 3 years of business activity.

The 3 steps above are the basis for a start-up – shareholder, team and technology. Only in next steps one can move to the technology preparation and searching for financing issues.

4. Technology Preparation means selecting or adapting the technology to meet the specific needs of end users. The technology must respond to defined, specific needs of the end users. The LUXWEX Project (applications on the earth) is currently a general technology for purifying water from selected pollutants at a low TRL.

At present, the monitoring system for changes in water purification legislation in the EU (which is currently ongoing) seems to have potential, particularly in the detection of drugs and hormones.

5. Searching for financing.

Once your problem is defined from the market and end users' perspective, and a technology-based solution is developed, you can begin searching for investors and funding. Both venture capital (VC) funds and private investors are viable options.

In the Polish market - there are for example foundations and starting platforms for innovators/start-ups and in EU we have e.g. EIC Accelerator. Additionally, large companies often announce competitions for start-ups.

It should be noted that the technology can be adapted by the LUXWEX Consortium to the defined problem, the specific needs of the end users, also before establishing a start-up. This reduces the start-up business risk. At the present time the LUXWEX Consortium can also get in contact with the industry representatives (potential buyers) presenting the standard technology offer. In the course of talks/negotiations the Consortium can decide which commercialization path to follow (e.g. spinoff or selling the rights directly to a company already present on the market).

Among the members of the LUXWEX Consortium there are also companies that could take over the IP rights (under an agreement of joint ownership of IP rights within the LUXWEX Consortium) as part of their existing business activities. This could lead to a creation of a quasi-spin-off which would greatly reduce the risk and cost related to the commercialization of the Project for the LUXWEX team and stakeholders who want to run a business based on the LUXWEX technology. Generally, the first step in this process involves an open discussion within the LUXWEX team to identify suitable individuals or team for this venture.

11 SWOT analysis

SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) analysis is a method for identifying and analysing internal strengths and weaknesses and external opportunities and threats that shape current and future operations and help develop strategic goals⁸¹. The name is an acronym for the four components the technique examines:

- Strengths: characteristics of the business or project that give it an advantage over others
- Weaknesses: characteristics that place the business or project at a disadvantage relative to others
- Opportunities: elements in the environment that the business or project could exploit to its advantage
- Threats: elements in the environment that could cause trouble for the business or project

The SWOT analysis for the Technology is presented in **Table 5** below.

Table 6. The SWOT analysis for the Technology.

	HELPFUL/POSITIVE	HARMFUL/NEGATIVE
INTERNAL	<p>STRENGTHS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. (Innovations) determining water quality, joining the trend of monitoring water for harmful substances. 2. Proven phenomena on which the technology is based. 3. Project consortium (scientific team). 4. The purpose of the Technology is to satisfy the basic human needs. 5. Modular technology, ability to implement a single part separately 	<p>WEAKNESSES</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No IP protection strategy, no state of the art. 2. No commercialization model chosen. 3. Low TRL of the Technology. 4. Lack of information in the Project’s materials (e.g. website) about other possible Technology applications on the earth. 5. Performed tests of the Technology without the use of dirty earthy water.
EXTERNAL	<p>OPPORTUNITIES</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Decreasing water resources on the earth – demand for such technology. 2. Market and social trends emphasizing technologies developed such in LUWEX. 3. European Green Deal, Fit for 55 Package. 4. Using the LUWEX Project for advertising, marketing activities aimed at commercialization (obtaining a partner for further work on LUWEX technology). 	<p>THREATS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Competitive solutions from companies and other technologies</i> Scaling (TRL increase) time and costs. 2. Long-time commercialization and implementation process. 3. Possible patent infringements (third party rights).

HARMFUL/NEGATIVE

The table above summarizes the identified indicators regarding SWOT analysis. Like any technology (new, innovative technology), the LUWEX Technology has weaknesses and threats. The main reason for the Technology's weaknesses /threat is the fact that it wasn't initially developed for the earth applications, however it should be kept in mind that it wasn't the goal of the LUWEX Project. Further negative issues related to the Technology can be described as follows:

- *No IP protection strategy, no state of the art; no commercialization model.* It is however, a quite typical case in R&D projects, especially at lower TRL levels. In new [next] projects [proposal from the recommendations section] or at the end of the current LUWEX Project, the consortium may develop this scope of data.

⁸¹ <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/swot.asp>

- *Low TRL of the Technology.* TRL is compliant with the Grant Agreement of the LUXWEX Project. Rated as low for the earth application. A typical research project in cooperation with business representatives aimed at commercialization should be at least at TRL 7.
- *Lack of information in the Project's materials (e.g. website) about other possible Technology uses on the earth.* The scientific team should develop a technological offer (select know-how elements of the LUXWEX Project for the earth applications). Then the technological offer could be promoted in order to find potential contractors/partners for its further development.
- *Performed tests of the Technology without the use of dirty earthly water.* It is important to note that if the Technology should be used in the applications on the earth, it must be verified in the proper real conditions (environment on the earth).
- *Competitive solutions from companies and other technologies.* As described in the market section, the competition for innovative technologies is intense involving business and scientific units). However, the market is very large and has many challenges. Therefore, market is very responsive to new technologies.
- *Scaling (TRL increase) time and costs and time-consuming commercialization / implementation process.* It is a general problem of research and development projects. A new project should be developed (e.g. as a continuation of LUXWEX project) regarding the Earth applications of the Technology.
- *Possible patent infringements (third party rights).* This is a threat, that can be assessed quite quickly through research conducted by a patent attorney.

It should be emphasized that weaknesses of the Technology can be mitigated [relatively at low cost] through further development of the Technology, e.g. through the development of an IP protection strategy, commercialization model (including suggestions of an entity selected to commercialize the Technology) or marketing activities. However, further works on increasing the TRL level will be more cost-intensive, however this is a general problem of R&D research.

HELPFUL/POSITIVE

The target industry for the Technology is strongly developing and is very promising. The purpose of the Technology is to satisfy basic human needs. Market and social (target for the analysed technology) can help implement such new technologies. Additionally, the research team, based on the experience from the current LUXWEX Project, can carry out next project with the objective to advance the TRL of the Technology to. To sum up, it seems possible to carry out a new project targeted at the development of the Technology for the earth applications.

- *Innovations for determining water quality, joining the trend of monitoring water for harmful substances.* As described in the above sections of this report, there are many ongoing works on the (legal) requirement to monitor the water for harmful substances such as pharmaceuticals, or even virus derivatives like for example COVID. Adaptation of the water quality module according to the LUXWEX Technology for a given element/spectrum seems feasible. This is one of the key advantages of the Technology.
- *Proven phenomena on which the Technology is based.* It is easier to implement technologies in the economy based on known phenomena, technologies that are improvements to those already implemented. The risk of failure is then lower.
- *Modular technology, ability to implement a single part separately.* The Technology consists of 3 modules: water purification module, water quality monitoring module, storage module. Each of these modules can function separately and has its final application. This is another key advantage of the Technology.
- *Project consortium (scientific team).* The recognized entities with experience in R&D projects build the LUXWEX consortium, which gives positive expectations towards the results and further possible research
- *The purpose of the Technology is to satisfy basic human needs.* The water is the basic raw material necessary for human life. The demand for water purification technologies is expected to continue to grow significantly.

- *Decreasing water resources.* As described in the report, the outlook for fresh water resources is constantly decreasing. Therefore, the demand for water purification technologies is expected to continue to grow significantly.
- *Market and social trends emphasize these types of technologies,* and e.g. European Green Deal, Fit for 55 Package also underline the importance of such research and developments. Big gap can be forecasted between the human needs for fresh water and declining water resources.
- *Using the LUXWEX Project for advertising, marketing activities aimed at commercialization (obtaining a partner for further work on LUXWEX Technology).* Possibility, after developing a technology offer of LUXWEX Project, for wider promotion of the Technology in the earth applications.

12 Recommendations

It should be noted that, there is no universal water treatment system. *So, who wins? Whose technology is going to be implemented?* The implementation success is influenced by: *team, investor, financial outlays, IP status, TRL, needs of the end users, investment turnaround time and technology efficiency in an individual case.*

Whoever has the greatest chance of winning will be the one who prepares the project [implementation technology] better [substantively and formally], and will carry out the project efficiently [verification at every important substantives and formal step].

In order to increase the chances of commercializing the LUXWEX Technology, it is recommended to:

1. Write down in one document all the essential know-how [for each module of the Technology and the whole Technology] related to the earth applications. Divide the parties' shares and the ownership of authors [% of contribution to the total property rights].
2. Develop a technology offer [also for a separate part for each module, information on the possibility of implementing each module separately should be presented] and carry out marketing activities. Develop a patent protection and commercialization strategy. Such activities are usually carried out by universities' Technology Transfer Offices in cooperation with the scientific team. Verify the obtained data in terms of implementation potential.
3. Acquire companies and potential end users of the Technology. Future research can be conducted on the end users and companies to identify technology parameters (what do they require). As a result, market guidelines for a new project could be identified in order to develop a technology (on the TRL8) corresponding to the needs. Verify the obtained data in terms of implementation potential [including the selection of modules for further R&D work].
4. Develop guidelines (technical, scientific) for a new implementation project based on the LUXWEX Technology and including recommendations from point 1 and 2 above regarding background IP. The LUXWEX Project's results allow for using them as a background IP for a targeted project, e.g. developing technology for the earth applications. The new project should include development works such as construction (e.g. in containers) of an installation according to the Technology and tests in real conditions. This new project should be implemented in a scientific-industrial partnership. The project should be verified at subsequent stages in terms of the implementation of its results by the project team.
5. The pilot implementation. Perform a technology audit and develop guidelines (design assumptions, mass balances, heat balances, etc.) for the pilot implementation. As a result, a functional and utility program and a feasibility study should be ready. The pilot implementation will contribute to the commercialization of the Technology on a wide scale.